

Surgeons Should Submit Pilonidal Disease Specimens To The Pathology Department For Histopathological Examination, If Pilonidal Disease Is Not Classified Within The Tissue Exemption List Of Their Institutions

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The necessity of histopathological examination of excised specimens after pilonidal disease surgery is still debated among medical professionals.

Methods: This study evaluates the ongoing debate about the need for histopathological examination after pilonidal disease surgery by reviewing of the existing literature between the years 1990 and 2023.

Results: Our examination of pathology department websites revealed that pilonidal disease specimens were not on the lists of those who were exempt from undergoing histopathological examination.

Conclusion: Healthcare institutions agree on the necessity of histopathological examination of specimens after pilonidal disease surgery.

Keywords: pilonidal sinus, histology

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INTRODUCTION

Pilonidal disease within the sacrococcygeal region frequently requires surgical intervention. The necessity of histopathological examination of excised specimens after pilonidal disease surgery is still debated among medical professionals. Some argue that routine examination is unnecessary due to the rarity of malignancy. However, proponents of histopathological analysis argue that sporadic cases of malignancy warrant a thorough examination to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment.

METHODS

This study evaluates the ongoing debate about the need for histopathological examination after pilonidal disease surgery. We conducted a thorough review of the existing literature through PubMed and Google Scholar between the years 1990 and 2023, analyzing viewpoints from both

ends of the spectrum. Furthermore, we surveyed the pathology websites of several healthcare institutions to determine their stance on exempting pilonidal disease specimens from examination.

RESULTS

An increasing number of surgeons claim that the possibility of detecting malignancy after pilonidal surgery is low. However, our examination of pathology department websites revealed that pilonidal disease specimens were not on the lists of those who were exempt from undergoing histopathological examination. This indicates a general agreement among healthcare institutions to conduct histopathological examination on pilonidal disease specimens

CONCLUSION

The conflicting views on histopathological examination following surgery for pilonidal disease highlight the necessity of standard protocols. Although some surgeons claim that malignancy associated with pilonidal disease is uncommon, even isolated instances emphasize the potential clinical significance. Our findings indicate that healthcare institutions agree on the necessity of histopathological examination of specimens after pilonidal disease surgery.

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